

1. Adult female *Tythrus* sp.

the same size as *C. lividipennis*. While *C. lividipennis* is green, *Tythrus* sp. is yellowish green when young and brown when mature (Fig. 1).

Inside the plant tissues, *Tythrus* sp. lay eggs that hatch in 8-9 d ($\bar{X} = 8.75 \pm 0.11$). The nymphal period is 13-16 d, with five instars: I = 2-4 d ($\bar{X} = 2.18 \pm$

2. Mean numbers of BPH attacked by *Tythrus* sp. brown mirid bug. Vertical lines on bars represent standard error.

0.13). II = 2-5 d ($\bar{X} = 3.75 \pm 0.28$), III = 2-4 d ($\bar{X} = 2.69 \pm 0.17$), IV = 2-4 d ($\bar{X} = 2.77 \pm 0.19$), V = 2-4 d ($\bar{X} = 3.00 \pm 0.13$).

The female adults attack BPH eggs at an average 14 eggs/d, with a maximum of 32 eggs (Fig. 2). They also prey on nymphs, but at lower rates. ■

A method for rearing diapausing rice yellow stem borer (YSB)

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YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) remains in diapause for 3-4 mo during the winter in Bangladesh. Study of the diapause with the use of rice stem-cuts to house diapausing larvae is difficult: stem-cuts need to be changed frequently, because they rot or dry up; diapausing larvae are disturbed and injured during transfer to new stem-cuts; and observation of larval development and pupation is virtually impossible because the rice stem-cuts are opaque.

To overcome these problems, we developed a simple method for rearing diapausing larvae, using 14-cm-long transparent plastic tubes (inner diameter about 4 mm, outer diameter 4.3 mm) (see figure). Two 1-cm-long cotton plugs are inserted into the tube at one end, with a 1.5 cm gap between them. One larva is introduced at the other end and the tube closed with another cotton plug.

We kept 86 tubes with larvae in three beakers wrapped in brown paper and containing a little water. The tubes stand

so that the ends with double plugs remain in contact with the water. The terminal plug soaked by the water in the beaker provides the required humidity in the tube. At the same time, the second plug remains dry to help keep the larva separated from the wet plug.

The beakers are placed in an insect rearing cage in the laboratory under normal photoperiod and temperature. The water in the beakers is changed at 4- to 5-d intervals and the beakers protected from ants.

Before pupation, the larva cuts a hole through the tube wall, seals it with membrane, forms a puparium, and then pupates. The moth emerges through the hole just as it does in a rice stem.

Among 86 larvae collected in the field and placed in the tubes in November, 20 escaped within 2 d by cutting holes through the tubes. The 20 probably were not in diapause. Of the 66 remaining larvae, 46 moths (70%) emerged (24 male and 22 female) in January and February.

Method for rearing diapausing rice yellow stem borer *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) in plastic tubes. Bangladesh, Nov 1989-Feb 1990.

Color of the plastic tube (blue, yellow, pink, and orange) had no significant effect on larval mortality and moth emergence. A few moths, mostly larger-size females, died inside the tubes. The larger moths need tubes a bit wider (5-6 mm). Tube walls should be thin (not more than 0.3-0.4 mm), so that larvae can cut a hole before pupation. ■

***Chilo auricilius* Dudgeon (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae), the correct name for the dark-headed stem borer (SB) found in the Philippines**

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We investigated the *Chilo* SB complex in rice, maize, sorghum, and sugarcane. Tillers were dissected and larvae found were reared individually in 20- × 3.5-cm tcst tubes. Pupae were transferred to plastic petri dishes for moth emergence. The abdomen of each moth was cut, cleared in a hot 10% solution of KOH, and washed with distilled water.

In 1,316 samples from throughout the Philippines, we found *C. suppressalis* (Walker) and *C. auricilius*, but not *C. polychrysus* (Meyrick). All larvae identified earlier as dark-headed SB were the gold-fringed borer *C. auricilius*. *C. auricilius* comprised 73% of the *Chilo* SB found in upland rice and 97-100% of those found in maize, sorghum, and sugarcane (Table 1).

The morphological similarity of the larvae and moths of the two species had led to earlier, erroneous records of *C. polychrysus* in the Philippines. Similar

Table 1. Composition of *Chilo* reared from 4 agricultural crops.

Crop	Borers examined (no.)	Composition (%)	
		<i>C. auricilius</i>	<i>C. suppressalis</i>
Rice			
Upland	482	73	27
Wetland	171	17	83
Maize	364	97	3
Sorghum	278	100	0
Sugarcane	21	100	0
Total	1316		

Table 2. Comparative moth morphology, life history, and host plant range of *C. auricilius* and *C. polychrysus*.^a

Criterion	<i>C. polychrysus</i> ^b	<i>C. auricilius</i>
Forewing of moth (see figure)	Terminal dots and subterminal line indistinct; subterminal line white with a few silvery scales; median line distinct, oblique and pale yellow brown; discal dot highly reduced; fringe slightly glossy; hindwing whitish to dirty cream	Terminal dots large; subterminal line represented by a row of metallic scales, and close to the apical margin; median line metallic line subterminal; discal dot visible; fringe shiny golden; hindwing light brown
Larva (see figure)	Dorsal setae D ₁ and D ₂ in the VIII abdominal segment nearly equidistant from dorsal line; adfrontal area of head same in color as the fronto-clypeal area	Seta D ₁ of VIII abdominal segment closer to the dorsal line than seta D ₂ ; adfrontal area of head paler than fronto-clypeal area
Development (d)	30-44	37-42
Egg incubation	4-7	6-8
Larva	20-30	22-24
Prepupa	No data	1
Pupa	6-7	8-9
Fecundity (no. of eggs/female)	73-488	5-233
Longevity (d)	2-5	6-9
Host plant range		
<i>Cyperus digitatus</i> Roxb.	+	-
<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i> P. Beauv.	-	+ ^c
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.)	-	+ ^c
<i>E. crus-galli</i> ssp. <i>hispidula</i> (Retz.) Honda	+	-
<i>E. frumentacea</i> Link.	-	+ ^c
<i>E. stagnina</i> (P. Beauv.)	-	+ ^c
<i>Eleusine indica</i> Gaertn.	-	+ ^c
<i>Erianthus munja</i> Roxb.	-	+ ^c
<i>Hemarthria</i> (= <i>Rottboellia</i>) <i>compressa</i> (L.f.) R. Br.	-	+ ^c
<i>Hymenache pseudointerrupta</i> C. Muell.+	-	-
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i> Salisb.	-	+ ^c
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i> (L.) Nees	-	+
Millet (name not specified)	+	-
<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	+	+
<i>Pennisetum purpureum</i> Schum.	-	+ ^c
<i>Saccharum officinarum</i> L.	-	+
<i>S. spontaneum</i> L.	-	+ ^c
<i>Sacciolepis interrupta</i> (Willd.)	-	+ ^c
<i>Sacciolepis myosuroides</i> (R. Br.) A. Camus	+	+ ^c
<i>Schlerostachya fusca</i> (Roxb.) A. Camus	-	+ ^c
<i>Scirpus grossus</i> L.f.	+	-
<i>Setaria italica</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	+	-
<i>S. palliolo-fusca</i> (Schum.) Stapf & C.E. Hubb.	+	-
<i>Sorghum bicolor</i> Moench	-	+
<i>S. halepense</i> (L.) Pers.	-	+
<i>Sporobolus diander</i> P. Beauv.	-	+
<i>S. indicus</i> R. Br.	-	+ ^c
<i>Triticum aestivum</i> L.	-	+
<i>Zea mays</i> L.	+	+
<i>Zizania aquatica</i> L.	+	-
<i>Z. lotifolia</i> Turcz.	+	-

^a+ = recorded host, - = no recorded host. ^bSource: Banerjee, S.N. and L.M. Pramanik, 1967. The lepidopterous stalk borers of rice and their life cycles in the tropics. pp. 103-126. In: The Major Insect Pests of the Rice Plant. The International Rice Research Institute. Johns Hopkins Press, Baltimore, Maryland. 729 p.; Anonymous. 1967. Rice Production Training Manual: Rice Insect Pests. IRRI, Los Baños. 182 p. ^cSource: Chaudhary, J.P. and S.K. Sharma, 1986. The stalk borer, *Chilo auricilius*. pp. 135-150. In: Sugarcane Entomology in India. Sugarcane Breeding Institute. Indian Council of Agricultural Research. Coimbatore, India. 564 p.

confusion may exist in countries where their distributions overlap: India, Thailand, Indonesia, and Malaysia.

Table 2 compares *C. auricilius* and *C.*

polychrysus on the basis of morphology, life history, and host plant range.

IRRI will accept *Chilo* moths for further comparison and identification. ■